

Title: Current Status and Projection of the Impact of Quantum Computing on Big Data Analytics, Machine Learning and AI

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INTRODUCTION:

Meta-Study to track and predict the impact of Quantum Computing on Big Data Analytics, Business Intelligence, and Machine Learning

AIM:

Providing executive guidance on assessing when investing into Quantum Readiness makes business sense.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Our company has partnered with several quantum computing (QC) vendors and is developing an architecture-independent development software stack. We have the capability to compile for various QC platforms and to perform benchmark comparisons on an ongoing basis. We also continuously monitor and compile benchmark papers, and catalog quantum algorithms, including their constraints as well as scaling behavior.

RESULTS:

We have derived a fine grain understanding of the various approaches to quantum computing, maturity differences, capabilities, and timelines, which we classify by hardware realization as well as logical architecture.

CONCLUSIONS:

The nascent quantum computing industry is in its infancy. No living IT practitioner lived through the time when modern computing was in a comparable early stage (i.e. when Hollerith tabulation machines were state of the art). As with the beginning of the modern computing age, there is an explosion of different incompatible approaches, and it is too early to declare a winning design. However, we can already identify trends and gauge the current and projected capabilities, which will empower businesses to make informed decisions when it comes time to invest into quantum computing capabilities.

KEYWORDS:

Quantum Computing, Quantum Machine Learning, Big Data, AI, Business Intelligence

BIOGRAPHY:

Henning Dekant is founder and the CEO of the Quantum Computing software company [Artiste QB-Net Inc.](#) He is a regular presenter and organizer of the [Toronto Quantum Computing and Big Data Meet-Up](#) (the largest of it's kind in North America).

Prior to founding his quantum machine learning start-up, he amassed over 15 years experience in the Big Data Software industry as product manager and consultant at SAS.

He holds a M.Sc. in Physics from the University of Heidelberg and a MBA from the Simon Business School of the University of Rochester.